

Toward enabling iCub to detect lies in everyday life

Dario Pasquali
Robotics Brains and Cognitive Sciences
ICT Directorate
University of Genova (DIBRIS)
Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
Genova, Italy
dario.pasquali@iit.it

Alessandra Sciutti
COgNiTive Architecture for
Collaborative Technologies
Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
Genova, Italy
alessandra.sciutti@iit.it

Francesco Rea
Robotics Brains and Cognitive Sciences
Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
Genova, Italy
francesco.rea@iit.it

Abstract—Social robots will be soon part of human society, where interactions are sometimes characterized by dishonesty. Hence, they will need to detect lies to better understand humans’ behavior, for instance, to assess who is trustworthy and provide better support in professions like teaching, caregiving, and law enforcement. In this manuscript, we present ongoing work, started 3-years ago, aimed at enabling the humanoid robot iCub to autonomously detect lies, in real-time, during an informal interaction. Our approach is based only on assessing the human partners’ cognitive load, through the measure of their pupil dilation. We show our scientific advancements and provide useful insights to both improve our system and to drive future developments in the field of lie detection in HRI.

Keywords—lie detection, cognitive load, HRI

I. INTRODUCTION

Lying is in general considered a bad behavior by society; however, we all use a multitude of white – or sometimes not – lies in our everyday interactions [1]. Soon, more and more robots will be part of our society; hence, they will need a set of tools to better understand humans’ behaviors and detect deception during common human-robot interactions. This could benefit robots themselves, helping them to understand who is trustworthy (i.e., in human-robot cooperation); but it could also benefit humans, for instance, with robots providing better support in professions like teaching, caregiving or law enforcement. The literature offers a plethora of methods to detect humans’ deceptions, however, most of them are either too expensive or complex to be ported to real-world human-robot interactions. For instance, the polygraph – the most commonly adopted method – requires multiple sensors and a group of experts to evaluate its measure – which is proved to be bypassable [2]. Recently, researchers proved it is possible to detect lies with a more portable combination of visual and acoustic features [3], with an accuracy of 66.1%. However, we speculate it would be better to rely on features more difficult to control voluntarily.

In our research, we explored the usage of pupillometry and pupil dilation to classify humans’ behavior as truthful or deceptive. Indeed, lying requires a cognitive effort due to the fabrication and maintenance of a consistent deception [4], and this reflects on measurable Task Evoked Pupillary Responses [5], like mean pupil dilation and latency to peak, which can be used to detect lies [6].

II. LIE DETECTION IN HRI

Firstly, in [7], we proved that the above-mentioned Task Evoked Pupillary Responses happen both in human-human and human-robot interaction. Indeed, the latter was not obvious because robots are known to elicit a higher cognitive load, mainly due to their complex shape, their unpredictable behavior, and the uncanny valley effect [8]. Hence, there was the risk that the effect of lie fabrication on cognitive load and pupil dilation were masked by the impact of being in presence

of a robot. We asked 28 participants to take part in an interrogatory as witnesses of two crimes (See Fig. 1). We showed them two short videos of robberies and asked them to tell the truth or lie, either to a human confederate or to the iCub humanoid robot. During the interrogation, participants wore a Tobii Pro Glasses 2 eyetracker, recording their pupil dilation, fixations, and saccades. Post-hoc, we found that both when lying to another human or to the robot iCub, participants’ average pupil dilation and the time to respond were higher than when telling the truth. Then, we trained two random forest classifiers. The first one was meant to classify generic participants’ answers as True or False. We trained it by splitting our dataset between participants; and it achieved an accuracy of 63% (AUCROC score of 0.69). The second model was trained within participants to classify further sentences of the same human partner; this model achieved an accuracy of 73% (AUCROC score of 0.77).

Fig. 1. Interrogation setup with the humanoid robot iCub (Top) and the human confederate (Bottom) from [7].

Hence, it is possible to enable the humanoid robot iCub to detect lies in human-robot interactions. However, interrogation scenarios are just a minimum subset of all the possible interactions humans and robots could engage in, and in which robots could take benefit by detecting lies. It would be far more useful to detect lies in common, informal human-robot interactions, potentially without letting the human being aware of this evaluation. We explored this scenario in [9]: after the interrogation, we asked the same participants to play a quick Magic Trick with iCub, while still wearing the Tobii eyetracker (See Fig. 2). They had to describe 6 pictures printed on cards to the robot, producing a creative and deceitful description for one of them – randomly drawn before the experiment – while describing what they saw for the others. After the last description, iCub – or rather the experimenter controlling it via Wizard of Oz – guessed the false card description. Post-hoc we found that participants’ average

pupil dilation was still higher when lying than when telling the truth. The effect was so clear that we were able to define a heuristic method to classify the descriptions, selecting as false the description related to the highest mean pupil dilation among the six. This simple heuristic detected participants' lies with an accuracy of 71.4% (against a chance level of 16.6%). Also, we trained a random forest classifier, balancing the dataset with the SMOTE algorithm, which achieved an F1 score of 83.3%. These preliminary results of lie detection in an informal HRI prompted us to make a standalone experiment out of this quick game. Moreover, we made the lie detection autonomous and real-time, enabling iCub to lead the whole interaction by itself.

Fig. 2. A participant interacting with iCub in the final version of the Magic Trick card game from iCub's point of view (Top) and Tobii eyetracker camera (Bottom) from [13].

III. TOWARD AN END-TO-END LIE DETECTOR

We developed an end-to-end (E2E) architecture (see Fig. 3) to enable the humanoid robot iCub to lead the Magic Trick card game and detect players' lies in real-time. The two main issues to solve were: (i) providing iCub with real-time streaming of players' pupil dilations; and (ii) enabling the robot to understand the turns of the interaction, i.e., to recognize when the players were describing the cards. Firstly, we developed the *Tobii Streamer* to stream and log in real-time Tobii eyetracker pupillometric measures on the YARP platform, which ensures the synchronization of the data stream. Then we placed 6 green marks on the table and 6 blue marks on the back of the cards (see Fig. 2). For each card, participants were instructed to take it, describe it while holding it in their hand, and placing it back on the green mark at the end of the description. The *Turn Detector* counted the number of green and blue blobs visible from iCub's left-eye camera and used it to annotate the Magic Trick turns. These annotations were streamed and logged on YARP to both enable iCub to segment the pupil dilation data stream and to facilitate the post-hoc analysis. Then, the *Secret Card Detector* segmented the pupil dilation stream based on the annotations, computed the average pupil dilation, and applied the heuristic method described above to detect the false card description. Finally, the *Magic Trick Controller* integrated the

other three components and controlled iCub accordingly. We validated the first version of our autonomous real-time pupil-based lie detector with 12 players; iCub was able to autonomously classify the card descriptions with an in-game accuracy of 90.3% [10].

Fig. 3. The final version of our E2E pupil-driven real-time lie detector system. See the text for the description of each component.

IV. LEARNING TO DETECT AND ADAPT TO LIARS

Building on the validated E2E system, we improved and extended the Magic Trick design. We replaced the six cards with a deck of 84 cards from the Dixit card game [11], meant to stimulate creativity (see Fig. 2, Bottom). Then, we designed a new version of the experiment composed of two phases: Calibration and Testing.

The *Calibration Phase* [12] resembles the Magic Trick as already presented. Players lied on a single card they knew in advance and iCub, after all the descriptions, detected it as the one related to the highest mean pupil dilation among the six and gave feedback to the players, asking them to show the right card in case of failure to correct its classification. Moreover, in the new version, iCub stored the average pupil dilation for the false card and truthful cards, learning an internal model of how the partner lies.

Then, in the *Testing Phase* [13], iCub exploited this knowledge to classify more card descriptions. Players drew 6 new random cards and were instructed to decide for each one whether they wanted to lie or tell the truth. iCub generated a classification, and gave feedback to the player, after each description by computing the Euclidean distance between the mean pupil dilation of the novel card and the two reference scores of True and False card descriptions learned before: the class associated with the lowest distance was then assigned as the label (see *Card Classifier* in Fig. 3).

We asked 39 participants to play with iCub. During the Calibration Phase, iCub could detect payers' false descriptions with an accuracy of 83.2%; while, in the Testing Phase, it classified players' descriptions with an accuracy of 70.8%. Post-hoc we verified that players' pupils were larger while lying than when telling the truth. Also, we tried to improve iCub performance both on (i) adapting to further lies of the same player and (ii) on classifying generic card descriptions. We developed an adaptive heuristic method that updates iCub's internal model after each classification of the Testing Phase. The two mean pupil dilation references are averaged with the new score at each description. This new method achieves an accuracy of 76.7% and it partially compensates for the fluctuation of players' pupil dilation (i.e., for illumination changes or other cognitive effort sources) that could happen during the interaction. Finally, we trained a

random forest classifier, splitting between participants on the data from the Testing Phase. This model, achieved an accuracy of 71.1% (AUCROC score of 0.73), proving iCub could use it to classify lies from novel partners.

V. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In this paper, we showed how the humanoid robot iCub can autonomously detect lies from human partners, in real-time, based only on their pupil-driven cognitive load assessment. Our end-to-end system is light and does not require any excessive computational power. Also, given the number of items (84 different cards, randomized for each player) and the few constraints involved, we speculate this system could be ported to different tasks and items consistent with real-life interactions. Moreover, it has the potential to be incrementally improved with prolonged interactions with the same human partner. However, our E2E system still has to be improved to be ported to real-life interactions. The main limitations are the need of an eyetracker and the presence of marks, both limiting system portability. The eyetracker was required to prove the feasibility of the approach, however, it will be necessary to rely on less invasive approaches to measure pupil dilation, like the recent developments on pupillometry measures from traditional RGB cameras [14]. Regarding the marks, we speculate it would be needed to develop a specific turn-detector solution based on the application scenario. For our setup, we could develop a solution based on object or voice activity detection. The use of pupil dilation per se represents both a benefit and a limitation. On one hand, it is a cognitive-load proxy not directly controllable, which means that liars cannot easily modulate voluntarily their pupil dilation to deceive the system. However, the measure is sensitive to other factors, like environment illumination, and other sources of cognitive load (i.e., stress or emotions). Hence, we speculate other sources of information need to be included to compensate for those limitations. An idea could be taking inspiration from humans.

Indeed, people can often detect lies, even if they mainly base their judgement on gut feelings [15]. To understand how to improve our system following the strategy adopted by human observers we ran an online survey [16]. We asked 117 responders to watch 20 videos of card descriptions from the Magic Trick Testing Phase. We selected 10 true and 10 false descriptions, and, for each subgroup, 5 correctly classified and 5 misclassified descriptions. For each one, responders had to classify it as true or false, report a confidence score on the classification (a number between 0-100) and provide an open-ended motivation for their judgement. Participants correctly classified only 53.9% of the videos – a score consistent with the accuracy in lie detection of 54% reported from the literature [15] – but, interestingly, they performed better and with more confidence on the descriptions iCub failed to classify. This suggests that liars sometimes could limit their cognitive load (and hence pupil dilation) fooling iCub. However, this causes them to exhibit other behaviors that could be spotted by the human responders.

Analyzing their motivations, participants focused both on how the actors described the card (‘details’, ‘pauses’, ‘(un)decided’) and how they behaved (‘gaze’, ‘voice’, ‘hands’). Based on these results, we speculate that combining the proposed pupillometry-based solution with the detection of behavioral cues suggested by the human observers could be the key solution to develop a robust lie detector in human-robot interaction. In the future, we will extend our system

including visual (i.e., body and hand posture) and acoustic (i.e., prosody) features, to make it more robust. Finally, we will need to define what the robot should do, from an ethical and social perspective, if it detects a liar. Indeed, wrongly accusing a human fellow of lying could compromise the social rapport with the robot (i.e., in fields like teaching, caregiving or law enforcement) or raise serious ethical issues. A potential solution could be for the robot to report this information to another trusted human, which will evaluate the best approach.

VI. CONCLUSION

With this manuscript, we presented our main findings on lie detection in human-robot interaction. We hope the presented approaches, results and hints could help other researchers shaping more social-aware robots and companions.

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